

Impact of facial occlusions in age estimation algorithms for forensic applications

Andrés Carofilis*, Deisy Chaves*, Alicia Martínez-Mendoza*, Eduardo Fidalgo*,
Victor González-Castro*, Enrique Alegre*

*Department of Electrical, Systems and Automation Engineering, Universidad de León, León, ES
Email:{andres.vasco, deisy.chaves, amartm, eduardo.fidalgo, victor.gonzalez, enrique.alegre}@unileon.es

Abstract—Age estimation is a critical tool for identifying minors and potential offenders in Child Sexual Exploitation Materials (CSEM). However, deep learning methods, which are the current state-of-the-art for age estimation, have low accuracy in predicting the age of minors and older adults due to a lack of data in existing datasets. In addition, facial occlusion, used to hide victims’ identities in some CSEM, can further impact the accuracy of age estimators.

This study evaluates the performance of six deep learning-based age estimators on facial images with and without occlusion. To simulate CSEM conditions, we used non-occluded datasets (i.e., FG-Net and APPA-REAL), and also synthetically occluded versions with black masks of these datasets. Results indicate that (i) age estimators are more affected by eye occlusion than by mouth occlusion and (ii) facial occlusion affects minors and the elderly more than other age groups. This study could serve as a reference for the estimation of age in forensic applications such as victim profiling on CSEM.

Index Terms—Age estimation, Deep Learning, Facial occlusion, CSEM

Type of contribution: *Research already published [1]*

I. INTRODUCTION

Age estimation from facial images is an important research in computer vision with applications in security and human-computer interaction [2], [3], [4]. The COVID-19 pandemic has led to an increase in the generation of Child Sexual Exploitation Material (CSEM), requiring new forensic tools to support Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) in victim identification. Accurate age estimation is critical for these tools, but remains challenging due to factors such as image quality, changes in expression, pose, illumination, and the aging process. Facial occlusion, which is common in CSEM, also affects the accuracy of age estimation because crucial features such as the eyes and mouth corners are not visible. Offenders add occlusion to victim images to make it difficult to identify them, so it is necessary to study the performance of multiple models with this type of data.

The summarized paper [1] evaluates the effect of occlusion on age estimation using six state-of-the-art deep learning models and two publicly available datasets labeled with apparent age, FG-Net [5], and APPA-REAL [6]. The authors also created synthetic versions of these datasets with eye and mouth occlusion to simulate CSEM conditions. The performance of the age estimators was evaluated using the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) computed for eight age groups between 0 and 70+. This study aims to provide a benchmark for age estimation in forensic applications and may be useful in the development of future models that are robust to occlusion.

II. METHODOLOGY

We assessed the performance of age estimators from faces under non-occluded and occluded conditions to establish an initial age estimation benchmark, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Three-step evaluation methodology for age estimation.

First, we selected two publicly available datasets for age estimation (FG-Net and APPA-REAL), composed of non-occluded images, to create eye and mouth-occluded versions of them by automatically drawing black masks. We manually inspected the non-occluded datasets and removed the images labelled with an incorrect age or without a face. After cleaning both datasets, FG-Net kept 1002 facial images with ages between 0 and 69, and APPA-REAL 6884 facial images with ages between 1 and 100.

Second, we performed eye occlusion to reproduce the conditions that might be present in some CSEM and mouth occlusion to simulate face masks. The occluded images were generated using the Multi-Task Cascade CNN (MTCNN) model to identify facial landmarks and determine the position and dimensions of the rectangular masks to cover the eyes and the mouth. The dimensions of the rectangle covering the eyes are 25% of the height and 95% of the width of the bounding box containing the face. The rectangle dimensions covering the mouth are the 25% and 55% of the height/width, respectively, of the face bounding box.

Third, we selected six age estimators and evaluated them using (a) the non-occluded datasets and (b) the synthetically occluded ones in terms of the MAE and the standard deviation of the MAE over eight age groups between 0 and 70+ years (i.e., 0–9, 10–19, 20–29, 30–39, 40–49, 50–59, 60–69, and 70+ years) to identify the age ranges where the models perform better. The models assessed are Deep Expectation (DEX) [7], Ordinal Regression with Multiple Output CNN

(ORD) [8], Deep Label Distribution Learning with Label ambiguity (DLDL) [9], Expectation of Label Distribution Learning (DLDLv2) [10], Mean-Variance Loss (MV) [11], and Leveraging Face Parsing Attention (FP-Age) [12].

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 2 shows the MAE and its standard deviation for each of the eight age ranges between 0 – 97 years. The results confirm that all models perform poorly in non-occluded and occluded images for pre-pubescent (MAE of 15.58 for 0 – 9 years), pubescent (10.54 for 10 – 19 years) and elderly people (11.65 for 60 – 97 years), compared to the other age groups (5.83 for 20 – 59 years). It could be due to the unbalanced data used for building the age estimators, which contain few examples from these three age groups. Besides, age estimators drop their performance when used with occluded images, being slightly more affected by eye occlusion than mouth occlusion. This indicates that estimators rely more on features from the eye region. MV performs best on non-occluded images on the FG-Net ($MAE = 6.42$) and the APPA-REAL ($MAE = 8.03$) datasets. In the case of the occluded versions of the datasets, FP-Age obtained the best performance on the FG-Net ($MAE = 9.90$ and $MAE = 9.66$ for eye and mouth occluded) and the APPA-REAL ($MAE = 11.97$ and $MAE = 10.71$ for eye and mouth occluded) datasets.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper compares six deep learning-based age estimators using non-occluded and occluded facial images from FG-Net and APPA-REAL datasets. The results show that models are more affected by eye occlusion than by mouth occlusion. Moreover, the models struggle to predict the age of minors and elderly individuals due to limited examples in training datasets. MV and FP-Age are the best-performing models on non-occluded and occluded images, respectively. The study provides a benchmark for age estimators and highlights the need for novel architectures robust to facial occlusion.

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Figure 2. Evaluation of the DEX, ORD, DLDL, DLDLv2, MV and FP-Age age estimators on the datasets FG-Net and APPA-REAL.

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